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MONETARY POLICIES AND THE PERFORMANCE OF ZENITH BANK BRANCHES IN UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study is an attempt to systematically assess the strength of the correlation between monetary policies and the development of the banking sector in Nigeria. The study, by extension, examines the strength of the correlation between Open Market Operations (OMO) and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. The study employed monetary theory as its theoretical framework. Both qualitative and quantitative methodologies were used in the collection and analysis of data. A simple random sampling technique was employed to select three out of the four Zenith Bank branches in Uyo, while the Taro Yamane formula was employed to select respondents for the study. The analysis of data was achieved using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study showed that there is a strong correlation between monetary policies and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. The study also revealed that when Zenith Bank Plc purchases government securities on open market operations, it increases the reserves of Zenith Bank Plc as a commercial bank and allows it to increase its loans and investment discount rate policy to alter the bank's borrowing cost, which controls the circulation of money in the economy. It was recommended, among others, that Zenith Bank Plc should be allowed to purchase government securities in the open market, as this can increase the reserve of Zenith Bank Plc and improve their loans, investments, and development.

Keywords: Monetary policies, Zenith Bank, Central Bank, Government Securities, Open market Operation (OMO)

Introduction

Monetary policy is associated with interest rates and availability of credit. Instruments of monetary policy have included short-term interest rates and bank reserves through the monetary base. Interest rates, while now thought of as part of monetary authority, were not “generally coordinated with the other forms of monetary policy during this time.

Monetary policy was considered an executive decision and was generally implemented by the authority,” with seigniorage (the power to coin). With the advent of larger trading networks came the ability to define the currency value in terms of gold or silver and the price of the local currency in terms of foreign currencies. This official price could be enforced by law, even if it varied from the market price (Agbonkhese and Asekome, 2013).

Paper money originated from promissory notes termed “jiaozi” in 7th century China. Jiaozi did not replace metallic currency and were used alongside the copper coins. The succeeding Yuan Dynasty was the first government to use paper currency as the predominant circulating medium. In the later course of the dynasty, facing massive shortages of specie to fund war and maintain their rule, they began printing paper money without restrictions, resulting in hyperinflation (Black, Hancock, and Passmore, 2010). With the creation of the Bank of England in 1694, which was granted the authority to print bills backed by gold, the idea of monetary policy as independent of executive action began to be established. The purpose of monetary policy was to maintain the value of the coinage, print notes that would trade at par to specie, and prevent coins from leaving circulation. The establishment of national banks by industrialising nations was associated then with the desire to maintain the currency's relationship to the gold standard and to trade in a narrow currency band with other gold-backed currencies. To accomplish this end, national banks, as part of the gold standard, began setting the interest rates that they charged both their own borrowers and other banks that required money for liquidity. The maintenance of a gold standard required almost monthly adjustments of interest rates (Blinder, Ehrmann, De Haan, and Jansen, 2008). Therefore, monetary decisions presently take into account a wider range of factors, such as:

- a. Short-term interest rates;
- b. Long-term interest rates;
- c. Velocity of money through the economy;
- d. Exchange rates;
- e. Credit quality;

Statement of the Problem

Banks play a vital role in a nation's economy. This is because of the functions carried out by banks and other financial institutions. Such roles include saving people's money for investment purposes, acting as an institution that carries out payment services that are checked, granting demand or transaction deposits, and undertaking commercial lending. This centrality in the economic system singles out the banking sector for much heavier regulation than any other financial institution and, if not checked or properly

administered, will lead to chaos and economic breakdown, hence the need for monetary policies such as open market operation (OMO), discount rate policy, reserve requirement, expansionary and contractionary interest rate, primary monetary policy, secondary monetary policy, primary and secondary wrapped together, and tertiary type of monetary policy.

This work seeks to analyse the impact of money policies on the growth of banking sectors, with particular reference to Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the impact of monetary policies on the growth of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Other subsidiary objectives included the following:

1. To assess the effect of open market operations (OMO) on the development of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State.
2. To determine the impact of the discount rate policy on the development of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State.
3. To ascertain whether the reserve requirement enhances development in the banking operations of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does Open Market Operations (OMO) affect the development of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State?
2. To what extent does the discount rate policy affect the development of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State?
3. To what extent does the reserve requirement enhance confidence in the operation of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State?

Statement of Hypotheses

- H₀:** There is no significant relationship between Open Market Operation (OMO) and the development of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo Branches, Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀:** There is no significant relationship between the discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State.
- H₀:** There is no significant relationship between reserve requirements and the development of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State.

Conceptual Framework

Money is simply anything of value that is accepted by the general public for the purpose of making transactions and settling debts. Money is used primarily as a means of exchange and plays an important role in the settlement of financial obligations. Money is regarded as a currency (notes and coins) because it is easily used in making payments. People use the terms "money and currency" interchangeably. However, money is more than currency in that it includes other things that are used for transactions. For example, in ancient civilization, couriers served as a medium of exchange. Today, quite a number of countries have their own currency or money in the form of coins and paper notes, which is widely accepted in exchange for goods and services as well as for debt settlement. The main reason currencies are generally accepted is because insurance is backed by law in Nigeria, the national currency (Naira and Kobo) is issued by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and it is the legal tender for the settlement of financial transactions. Money can also be used for purposes beyond the settlement of financial obligations or as a medium of exchange. It can serve as a unit of account and, hence, can be used in determining the value of goods and services. Money also acts as a standard for measuring the value of goods and services. Besides these functions, money also acts as a standard for deferred payments and a store of value.

Money supply is the sum of all money or monetary assets that can easily be converted to cash in an economy at a specific time. It is often referred to as money stock since it is measured at a particular point in time. Money supply is closely monitored by the monetary authority, the Central Bank, because if the rate of increase in money supply is consistently greater than the rate of increase in total output of goods and services in the economy, there could be a general increase in the domestic price of goods and services, a situation generally referred to as inflation.

Money supply is measured differently by countries depending on how developed the financial system is. In Nigeria, the different measures of money supply known as monetary aggregates include monetary base, narrow money, and broad money. The monetary base, also known as the base money, high-powered money, or reserve money, is the sum of currency outside banks, currency in the vault of deposit money banks (DMBs), and cash reserves of DMBs with the Central Bank (R). The sum of currency outside banks and currency in the vault of DMBs is called currency in circulation (C). The monetary base is the most liquid measure of money supply and the lowest classification of money, often denoted as Mo. The monetary base can be controlled by the monetary policy actions of the Central Bank. This is because some of its components (bank reserves) are directly under the Central Bank's control. The measure of money supply is very important in monetary management. This is because central banks control money supply through the measure of money.

Monetary Policy

Central banks often adopt certain methods or techniques (strategies) to achieve the ultimate goals of monetary policy. It involves choosing a goal (such as inflation or the normal GDP exchange rate) or an intermediate variable (such as the money supply or market rate) and settling a desirable variable (or target) of the variable the Central Bank intends to achieve using the instruments of monetary policy.

Interest rate targeting is also similar to monetary targeting, but the target variable is the interest rate (mostly the short-term interest rate or interbank rate). The strategy involves setting the minimum interest rate, usually the overnight interbank rate, at a level considered good enough to achieve monetary policy objectives. The interest rate directly and naturally influences the money supply to a point that keeps macroeconomic variables healthy when appropriately set. Other interest rates that can be targeted, depending on the country, include the “minimum one-week re-financing credit rate.” In this type of monetary policy strategy, the most common instrument used by the central bank is open market operations (OMO), including re-purchase agreements (repo and reverse repo) and/or auctions of promissory notes issued by the central bank. The level of the interest rate is determined either by the result of the periodic auctions or by unilaterally setting a minimum auction rate with the ultimate goal of restoring the liquidity condition of the banks.

Exchange rate targeting, or exchange rate peg (as it is otherwise called), is a monetary policy strategy that involves fixing the value of a national currency in terms of the currency of another nation considered strong. The measure of a nation's strength is the level of its inflation rate. Thus, a nation that adopts exchange rate targeting as a monetary policy strategy simply pegs its currency to be responsive to the rate of inflation of the identified minor country. This is so under the assumption that if a fixed exchange rate is sustained, the gap between the inflation rates of two countries should even out. This implies that a country with a high inflation rate would leverage a low-inflation country for effective implementation of monetary policy. The exchange rate targeting can be adopted using any of the following three approaches: currency board management, fixed exchange rate, and dollarization strategies.

Instruments of Monetary Policies Theory

The policy instruments are of two kinds; they are:

- i. Indirect quantitative or general
- ii. Direct quantitative or selective.

These affect the levels of aggregate demand through the supply of money cost of money, and availability of credit. The first category includes: open market operation, discount rate, changing reserve requirements, and bank rate variations. They are meant to regulate the overall level of credit in the economy through commercial banks. Selective credit control aims at controlling specific kinds of credit.

They are discussed under the following headings:

1. Open Market Operation

This refers to the sale and purchase of securities by Zenith Bank in the money market. When prices are rising and there is a need to control them, Zenith banks sell securities. The reserves of commercial banks are reduced, and they are not in a position to lend money to individuals and corporations. Further investments are discouraged, and the rise in price is checked. On the contrary, when recessionary forces start in an economy, Zenith Bank buys securities from business communities and commercial banks, thereby increasing their reserve. Investment, output, income, and aggregate demand rise (Agbonkhese and Asekome, 2013).

2. Discount Rate Policy

The discount rate policy is the interest rate reserve. Banks charge commercial banks for short-term loans. Federal Reserve lending at the discount rate complements open market operations in achieving the target federal funds rate and reserves as backup sources of liquidity for commercial banks.

The discount policy is a tool taken by the CBN to control the money circulation by raising or lowering interest rates. If the CBN raises bank rates, the aim is to reduce the money supply in the economy. Therefore, the amount of money will be reduced. The policy to raise bank rates is to press inflation (Blinder, Ehrmann, Haan, and Jansen, 2010).

3. Changes in the Reserve Requirement Ratio

This system was first adopted in the USA as a suggestion by Keynes 'Treatise on Money' as a monetary devise. In every organised financial economy, there is a certain percentage with Zenith Bank. When prices are rising, the Zenith bank raises the reserve ratio. The bank is required by law to keep more at the Zenith bank. They lend less when their reserve is reduced, and they lend less. The volume of investment, output, and employment are adversely affected.

On the contrary, when the reserve ratio is lowered, the commercial bank's reserves rise, thereby lending more, and economic activities are favoured (Black, Hancock, and Passmore, 2010).

Theoretical Framework

Monetary policy and banking sector theories have evolved rapidly over time, dominated by dissimilarities, obscurities, inconclusiveness, and cross-currents (Brunner and Meltzer, 1972). Banking growth theories and monetary policy predate as far back as classical quantity theory (QTM) (Gali, 2008). However, modern theories only came to the fore in the 1930s, with the Keynesian Liquidity Preference Theory, followed by monetarism (a manifestation of the OTM) and subsequently by several theories, such as the New Classical Real Business Cycles, the New Keynesian Model, and the New Consensus Model (NCM), which have been at the centre of monetary policy analysis over the past two or so decades (Good friend and King, 1997; Aretis and Sawyer, 2008). Over the years, the short-run and long-run impact of monetary policy on real variables, in particular on output, has remained ambiguously at the centre of research (Walsh, 2003). Most studies have focused largely on monetary neutrality in the long run and on developed countries (Asongu, 2014). This research work provides an eclectic review of theoretical literature on the impact of monetary policy and banking sectors in Nigeria in the short-run and long-run. The essence of this study is to show different focus from different countries and country groups, periods and proxy variables, and different econometric methodologies and theoretical literature on the relationship between monetary policy and banking sectors in Nigeria.

Keynes was sceptical of the effectiveness of monetary policy when the economy was in a liquidity trap and also because of uncertainty in the financial markets. Keynes supported a more pronounced role for fiscal policy. The assumption of an exogenous money supply in both classical and Keynesian theories has been challenged and discarded in subsequent and modern theories (Romer, 2006). Prolonged low interest rates in Keynes's theory are also believed to have distortions in the form of unsustainable asset price bubbles (Schwartz, 2009).

Monetarist theory came to the fore in the 1950s, drawing its cornerstone from the QTM and assuming that velocity in the quantity theory of money is generally stable, which implies that nominal income is largely a function of the money supply (Friedman and Schwartz, 1963; Friedman, 1968, 1970). The monetarists upheld the principle of trade-off between inflation and output but reformulated the Philips curve in terms of real wages and not nominal wages (Gottschalk, 2005). Equilibrium in the labour market is obtained at a natural rate, and assumptions of sticky wages prevail. The nominal rigidities in wages and prices imply that monetary policy affects real income in the short run (stabilisation); an increase in money stock would have a temporary increase in real output (GDP) and employment in the short run but no impact in the long run due to the countervailing effect of an increase in the general price. The money supply in the long

run is inflationary; thus, the theory assumed long-run monetary neutrality. There is substantial evidence found in even recent literature to support this (see, among others, Bernanke and Mihov, 1998; Bullard, 1999; Nogueira, 2009).

Empirical Literature

The effect of monetary policy is a first issue in macroeconomics, and it has attracted comments from different scholars both in developed and developing countries.

Ojo (1999) regards monetary policy during much of the 90's as generally restrictive, yet the money supply (in this case, M2) increased persistently and well beyond the established growth rate target.

Sanusi (2001) goes further back to a period (1959–1969) when Nigeria's monetary policy was deliberately expansionary during this period. As the Treasury bill rate was reduced from 5% in 1960 to 3.5% in 1964, M2 rose at an annual rate of 44% between 1960 and 1994 and to 84% in 1968–1970.

Monetary policy strategy refers to how the first bank carries out monetary policy actions (Mish Kin, 2001). A first feature of the different forms of monetary policy strategy is the choice of the numerical anchor. Thus, each of the three basic types of monetary policy strategies uses a different nominal anchor. Monetary targeting involves the use of information conveyed by the monetary aggregate to conduct monetary policy. Monetary targeting occurs in at least two forms. The first is the rigid Friedman-type, in which the chosen monetary aggregate is kept on a constant growth rate path as a result of the forces of monetary policy. Second is the flexibility variety, which may involve a set of monetary aggregates, each of which is allowed to grow at different rates.

According to "Odozi," the conduct of monetary policy goes through three inter-related stages, namely:

- a. Policy Formulation Stage
- b. Implementation Stage
- c. Review Stage

A number of empirical studies confirm that monetary policy is crucial for economic growth. Havi and Enu (2014) examine the relative importance of monetary policy and fiscal policy on economic growth in Ghana over the period of 1980 to 2012. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation results revealed that money supply as a measure of monetary policy had a significant positive impact on the Ghanaian economy. Vinayagathan (2013) estimates the impact of monetary policy on the real economy using a seven-variable structural VAR model by utilising monthly time series data from Sri Lanka covering the period from January 1978 to December 2011. The study found that interest rate shocks had a significant impact on output, in accordance with economic

theory. It also finds that a positive money shock provides significant but inconsistent results on output. Output declines rather than increases.

Kareem et al. (2013) used the OLS method and correlation matrix to examine the impact of fiscal and monetary policies on the economic growth of Nigeria, with particular reference to the period between 1998 and 2008. They found that monetary variables of narrow money and broad money are significant policy variables that positively affect economic growth (the real GDP growth rate) in Nigeria.

Davodi et al. (2013) used three variants of structural VARs on monthly data sets from 2000 to 2010 to determine MTMs in the East African Community. The study found that MTM tends to be generally weak when using standard statistical inferences but somewhat stronger when using non-standard inference methods. An expansionary monetary policy (a positive shock to reserve money) increases output significantly in Burundi, Rwanda, and Uganda. However, they also found that an expansionary monetary policy (a negative shock to the policy rate) increases output in Burundi, Kenya, and Rwanda. Berg et al. (2013) used the narrative approach pioneered by Romer and Roomer (1989) to examine monetary transmission mechanisms in the tropics, with a focus on four East African countries (Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania, and Rwanda). They found that there was clear evidence of a working transmission mechanism: after a large policy-induced rise in the short-term interest rate, lending and other interest rates rise, the exchange rate tends to appreciate, and output growth tends to fall.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher employs a survey design for the purpose of obtaining data to enable the researcher to test formulated hypotheses or answer research questions. The essence of the survey research design was to observe the sample subjects or variables without any attempt to manipulate or control them and to determine the interrelatedness between the monetary policies and banking sectors in Nigeria. The major characteristic of all survey research designs was a lack of control, but they focused on people's opinions, behaviours, attitudes, and motivations.

Uyo L.G.A. is one of the 31 local government areas in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Uyo, as the capital of Akwa Ibom State, constitutes the area of research for the study. Zenith Banks Plc is located at Udoudoma Banking Layout, Abak Rd., Aka Rd., and Oron Rd., Uyo. The population of the study comprises all staff members of Zenith Bank, Uyo branches in Akwa Ibom State, and their stakeholders. The total number of Zenith bank staff members in Uyo at the time of the study was 400, while other stakeholders were 2,100. Thus, the total population of the study was 2500.

From the population of 2500, a sample size of 345 was obtained using the Taro-Yamane formula. The 345-sample size was selected from three out of four branches of Zenith Bank Plc. Uyo using proportionate sampling techniques. This implies that in each of the branches, 115 staff and stakeholders were randomly selected for the study.

The study employed a multi-stage procedure. This is because the distribution of the target population was so complex that the researcher needed more than one sampling technique to select the sample. First of all, the researcher used simple random sampling to select 3 Zenith Bank branches out of the 4 Zenith Bank Plc. branches in Uyo: Aka Road branch, Uyo; Oron Road, Uyo; Abak Road, Uyo; and Udoudoma Banking Layout, Uyo. The choice of simple random sampling was informed by the fact that it ensures that every branch in the 3 Uyo L.G.A. was given equal opportunity to prepare for the selection process without any form of control or manipulation.

Purposive sampling technique was also used by the researcher to select the respondents from the different categories of respondents from the three branches of Zenith Bank Plc selected for the study.

The choice of purposive sampling was made because it ensured certain characteristics or features of the population needed to be represented in the sampling process. The study also used the snowball sampling technique to select the respondents. This became necessary because the location of some respondents was very difficult for the researcher, except for the introduction of such respondents to the researcher by other respondents who knew their locations.

A questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection for the study. The questionnaire contained introductory notes. And for the purpose of allaying fears and also ensuring the confidentiality of the respondents, a period of one week was given to the respondents to complete and return the questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of sections A and B. Section A comprises 5 questions that border on the personal information of the respondents, while Section B consists of 10 questions aimed at providing explanations for the topic of investigation.

The interview schedule granted the researcher and the field assistants the opportunity to probe. A total of 400 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents in order to elicit responses on monetary policies and banking sectors. 330 copies out of 345 questionnaires were useful for the study. Five copies of the questionnaire were discarded for inconsistency in their responses; eight copies were dropped by the researcher for non-completion of the questionnaires; and seven copies were not returned at all. The response rate was set at 90%, which is considered reasonable. The sources of data collection used in this research work were primary and secondary data.

Simple percentages (%) were used by the researcher to analyse the background features of the respondents. Whereas, the choice of the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (y) by the researcher to test formulation hypotheses was informed by the assumptions:

- i. That it has interval or ratio level of measurement
- ii. That it has normal sampling distribution of the parameter
- iii. That the different branches have been randomly selected
- iv. The different branches are independent of one another.

By choosing Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (y), the researcher is interested in measuring the strength of the relationship between monetary policies and banking sectors in Nigeria, with particular reference to Zenith Bank Plc branches in Akwa Ibom State, and not whether there is an existence or absence of a linear or non-linear relationship between the variables.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Respondents: Banking Staff and Customers

This section presents the banking staff and customers of the respondents based on sex, age, marital status, educational attained and occupation.

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Socio-economic Characteristic of the Respondents

	Socio-economic Characteristics of Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	210	63 – 64
	Female	120	36 – 36
	Total	330	100
Age in Years	20 – 30	50	21.21
	31 – 40	70	15.15
	41 – 50	80	24.24
	51 and above	130	39.40
	Total	330	100
Marital Status	Single	60	18.18
	Married	180	54.55
	Divorced	25	7.58
	Widowed	65	19.69
	Total	330	100

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Educational attainment	Primary	40	12.12
	Secondary	190	57.58
	Tertiary	100	30.30
	Total	330	100
Occupation	Public servants	80	24.24
	Bank staff	57	17.27
	Contractors	64	19.40
	Civil servants	86	6.06
	Farmers	43	13.03
	Total	330	100

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

The table above shows the percentage distribution of the respondents' socio-economic characteristics. Of the three hundred and thirty (330) respondents, two hundred and ten (210) respondents, representing 63.64%, were male, while one hundred and twenty (120) respondents, representing 36.36%, were female.

It can be said here that more male respondents participated in the study than female respondents. This unequal sex distribution of respondents in the course of the research does not in any way affect the result of the study; rather, it explains the fact that male respondents are always more eager and willing to participate in social enquiries than their female counterparts.

The table also shows fifty (50) respondents were within the age group of 20–30 years, representing 21.21%; seventy (70) respondents, representing 15.15%, were within the age group of 31–40 years; eighty (80) respondents, representing 39.40%, were within the age group of 51–50 years; and one hundred and thirty (130) respondents, representing 39.40%, were within the age range of 50 and above.

The table also showed that out of three hundred and thirty (330) respondents, sixty (60), representing 18.18%, were single, one hundred and eighty (180), representing 54.55%, were married, twenty-five (25) respondents, representing 7.58%, were divorced, and sixty-five (65) respondents, representing 19.69%, were widowed.

The table also presented the distribution of respondents' educational attainment. Out of the three hundred and thirty (330) respondents, forty (40) respondents, representing 12.12%, have primary education, while one hundred and ninety (190)

respondents, representing 57.58%, have secondary education, and one hundred (100) respondents, representing 30.30%, have tertiary education.

The table showed that eighty (80) respondents, representing 24.24%, were public servants; fifty-seven (57) respondents, representing 17.21%, were staff of Zenith Bank Plc; sixty-four (64) respondents, representing 19.40%, were contractors; eighty-six (86) respondents, representing 26.06%, were civil servants; and forty-three (43) respondents, representing 13.03%, were farmers.

Testing of Hypotheses

As earlier stated, this study on monetary policies and banking sectors in Nigeria employs Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (y) as the basic statistical tool for testing the formulated hypotheses, so that the strength of correlation between variables can properly be measured without withering one variable from the other.

The formula for Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (y) is given below as:

$$r = \frac{n\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

- n = the numbers of pairs of scores
- xy = the sum of the products of the paired scores
- x = the sum of the scores on the variable x
- y = the sum of the scores on variables y
- x² = the sum of squares on variable x
- y² = the sum of squares on variable y.

The hypotheses were tested in line with the structured statements used in the questionnaire. Degree of freedom (df) = the number of pairs of scores minus two, which means n -2. The level of significance is 0.05. The decision was taken based on some inherent properties of the statistical technique, which are stated below:

- (a) y takes values between -1 and + 1 i.e. -1 < y < + 1
- (b) if y = +1 we say there is a positive correlation between the two variables.
- (c) if y = -1 we say there is a negative correlation between the two variables only.

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Testing of the Hypothesis One

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Open Market Operation (OMO) and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between Open Market Operation (OMO) and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

To test these hypotheses, responses to question 7 from the questionnaire were taken as observed values.

Table 2: Opinion on whether there is or no significant correlation between Open Market Operation (OMO) and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

Categories of Respondents	Yes (x)	No (y)	Total
Public servants	50	30	80
Bank staff	30	27	57
Civil servants	50	36	86
Contractors	40	24	64
Farmers	30	13	43
Total	200	130	330

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Table 3: Showing the calculation of the strength of correlation between OMO and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State

x	x ²	y	y ²	xy
50	2500	30	900	1500
30	900	27	729	810
50	2500	36	1296	1800
40	1600	24	576	960
30	900	13	169	390
Total 200	8400	130	3670	5460

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

The calculated test of significance of “y” value = 0.7634 or 0.76.

The degree of freedom (d/f) = 3

The level of significance = 0.05

The table value under 3 degrees of freedom at 0.05.235 (Appendix) (a) for the calculation of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient “y” value.

Decision

The calculated test of significance of the “y” value is 0.71, and the table value is 2.35. Since the calculated value is greater than the table value, the null hypothesis (Ho1), which states that there is no significant correlation between OMO and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State, is therefore rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (Hi), which states that there is a significant correlation between OMO and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. This implies that there is a strong correlation between Open Market Operation and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State, as it increases their loans to customers' investments and the development of the bank.

Testing of Hypothesis Two

H₀: There is no significant relationship between discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

In order to test hypothesis two, responses to question 8 from the questionnaire were used; hence, the responses to question 8 were taken as observed values.

Table 4: Opinion on whether there is or no significant relationship between discount rate policy and development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

Categories of Respondents	Yes (x)	No (y)	Total
Public servants	50	30	80
Bank staff	30	27	57
Civil servants	55	31	86
Contractors	42	22	64
Farmers	30	13	43
Total	207	123	330

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Table 5: Showing the calculation of the strength of correlation between discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State

x	x ²	y	y ²	xy
50	2500	30	900	1500
30	900	27	729	810
55	3025	31	921	1705
42	1764	22	484	924
30	900	13	169	390
Total 207	9089	123	3243	5329

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

The calculated test of significance of “y” value = 0.7052 or 0.71.

The degree of freedom (d/f) = 3

The level of significance = 0.05

The table value under 3 degrees of freedom at 0.05 = 2.35

(Appendix) (b) for the calculation of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (y) value.

Decision

The calculated test of significance of “y” is 0.7052, or 0.71, and the table value is 2.35. On the strength of this result, the null hypothesis (H_{02}), which states that there is no significant correlation between discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State, is hereby rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1), which states that there is a significant correlation between discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State, as it helps in altering the borrowing cost, controls the circulation of money, and assists in making financial stability in the market.

Testing of Hypothesis Three

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between reserve requirement and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between reserve requirement and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

In order to test these hypotheses, the responses to question 14 were used. Hence, the responses to question 14 were taken as observed values.

Table 6: Opinion on whether there is or no significant relationship between reserve requirement and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

Categories of Respondents	Yes (x)	No (y)	Total
Public servants	50	30	80
Bank staff	30	27	57
Civil servants	50	36	86
Contractors	40	24	64
Farmers	30	13	43
Total	200	130	330

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

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Table 7: Showing the calculation of the strength of correlation between reserve requirement and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State

x	x ²	y	y ²	xy
50	2500	30	900	1500
30	900	27	729	810
50	2500	36	1296	1800
40	1600	24	576	960
30	900	13	169	390
Total 200	8400	130	3670	5460

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

The calculated test of significance of “y” value = 0.7634 or 0.76.

The degree of freedom (d/f) = 3

The level of significance = 0.05

The table value under 3 degrees of freedom at 0.05 = 2.35

(Appendix) (c) for the calculation of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (y) value.

Decision

The calculated test of significance of the “y” value is 0.76, and the table value is 2.35. On the strength of this result, the null hypothesis (H₀), which states that there is no significant correlation between reserve requirement and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State, is hereby rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H₁), which states that there is a significant correlation between reserve requirement and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State, is accepted. This result is an affirmation of the fact that the monetary policies have been fully observed and practiced by Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State, as they increase the supply of money in the economy, investments, output, and even employment.

Discussion of Findings

For hypothesis one, tables two and three revealed that there is a strong correlation between OMO and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This finding aligns with existing literature (Vinayagathan, 2013) that the OMO is enhanced by monetary policy. This is evidenced by the fact that, due to the strong correlation between OMO and the development of Zenith Bank Plc Uyo branches, more branches have been created in Akwa Ibom State. Tables four and five were used to examine

hypothesis two, and they revealed that there is a strong correlation between the discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. The finding equally gave support to the literature of the Central Bank of Nigeria (2010) that discount rate policy alters the banks borrowing costs and hence the rates they charge on loans, and adjustment of the discount rate policy is considered a tool to combat recession or inflation by the Central Bank. Because of this strong correlation between the discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc Uyo branches, the circulation of money in the economy is controlled, including the borrowing costs. The study also discovered that a discount rate policy is used by Zenith Bank, Uyo, to control borrowing costs and the amount charged on loans given to customers.

Hypothesis three was evaluated using tables six and seven. They revealed that there is a strong correlation between reserve requirements and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. This finding also aligned with the literature of the Central Bank of Nigeria (2005), which states that reserve requirements are a tool used by the central bank to increase or decrease money supply in the economy and influence interest rates, investments, output, and the reduction of employment, which led to the retrenchment of staff by Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. Finally, these findings of the study revealed that open market operations, the discount rate policy, and the reserve requirement have contributed immensely to the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches.

Summary

The essence of the study was to assess the strength of the correlation between monetary policies and banking sectors in Nigeria, with particular reference to Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. But the hypotheses have proven invalid, which means that there exists a significant correlation between monetary policies and banking sectors in Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

The study also revealed that there is a strong correlation between the discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches.

The study equally showed that there is a strong correlation between reserve requirements and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

Conclusion

The study was an attempt to systematically assess the strength of the correlation between monetary policies and banking sectors in Nigeria, with particular reference to Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. The study revealed that there is a strong correlation between monetary policies and banking sectors in Zenith Bank Plc,

Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. The study concludes that there are monetary policies in banking sectors in Nigeria that have affirmed the development of banks in Nigeria.

The study also concludes that there is a strong correlation between the Open Market Operation (OMO) and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State. The study further concludes that there is a significant correlation between the discount rate policy and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

The study finally concludes that there is a strong correlation between the reserve requirement and the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made, as these could improve the development of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

1. Zenith Bank branches in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State should be allowed to purchase government securities in the open market, as this can increase the reserve of Zenith Bank Plc and improve their loans, investments, and development.
2. Zenith Bank branches in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State should use a discount rate policy to control the circulation of money in the economy and borrowing costs.
3. Zenith Bank Plc should be allowed to use reserve requirements (a tool used by central banks) to increase or decrease the supply of money in the economy, as this will impact the areas of interest rate, investments, output, and employment of Zenith Bank Plc, Uyo branches, Akwa Ibom State.

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